

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

SUSTAINABILITY OF CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTION IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE: TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACHES AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract

Climate change has a complex and increasing impact on the construction industry, transforming the requirements for design, selection of building materials, organization of construction production and operation of buildings and structures. An increase in average annual temperatures, an increase in the frequency of extreme weather events, as well as changes in precipitation patterns and groundwater levels are creating new risks for construction processes and capital construction facilities.

The purpose of the study is to analyze the impact of climate change on the construction industry and substantiate technological solutions aimed at increasing the sustainability and adaptability of the industry.

The article analyzes the influence of temperature changes and extreme weather events on the technological processes of construction. Modern innovative materials, digital technologies, energy-efficient and climate-adaptive solutions, as well as organizational and technological approaches that ensure the sustainability of construction production are considered.

Special attention is paid to the conditions of the Republic of Armenia, for which climate change is accompanied by significant economic risks and increasing vulnerability of key industries. It is shown that the introduction of adaptation technologies contributes to improving the reliability, safety and environmental efficiency of construction facilities.

Keywords: climate change, construction industry, sustainable construction, technological solutions, adaptation, digitalization, energy efficiency, climate risks, innovative materials.

Introduction

Global climate change is one of the key challenges of our time and has a significant impact on the socio-economic development of countries. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), there is a steady increase in global temperature, changing precipitation patterns, and an increase in the frequency of extreme weather events [3,4].

The construction industry is one of the most resource-intensive and climate-dependent sectors of the economy [6, 13]. Production processes on construction sites directly depend on weather conditions, and the durability and reliability of buildings and structures are determined by the ability of structures to adapt to changing climatic stresses. Climatic changes are manifested in an increase in average annual temperatures, an increase in the frequency of extreme weather events (heavy rainfall, droughts, hurricanes), as well as changes in hydrological regimes [3,4]. This affects all stages of the life cycle of capital construction facilities, from design to operation [11, 18]. At the same time, the construction industry is a significant source of greenhouse gas emissions, which reinforces the need for a transition to sustainable and adaptive development models.

The problem is particularly relevant for the Republic of Armenia, which is characterized by a high climatic vulnerability of the economy, which increases the risks for the construction sector [16].

The purpose of the study is to analyze the impact of climate change on the construction industry and substantiate technological solutions for its adaptation.

Scientific novelty

The scientific novelty lies in a systematic interdisciplinary approach to assessing the impact of climate change on construction production, including technological, organizational and economic aspects.

At work:

- an integrated approach to the analysis of climate risks in construction is proposed;
- modern technological solutions for adapting the construction industry are systematized;
- The patterns of transformation of organizational and technological processes are revealed;
- The relationship between climatic factors and the economic sustainability of the construction sector has been established (using the example of the Republic of Armenia).

Research methodology

The research is based on a systematic approach that considers construction production as a set of inter-related technological, organizational and economic processes.

Methods used:

- analysis and generalization of scientific literature;
- comparative analysis of the influence of climatic factors;
- structural and functional analysis of construction processes;
- analysis of statistical and economic data;
- systematization of technological adaptation solutions.

The information base consists of scientific publications, reports from international organizations, and statistical data reflecting climate and economic risks.

Economic consequences of climate change and their impact on the construction industry (using the example of the Republic of Armenia)

Climate change in the Republic of Armenia is gaining pronounced economic importance, forming long-term macroeconomic and sectoral risks.

Over the past 25 years, climate-related disasters (droughts, floods, hail, landslides) have led to losses exceeding 1.5 billion US dollars, which is equivalent to about 0.6% of GDP annually [6].

Additionally, there is an increase in the vulnerability of key sectors of the economy, including agriculture, energy, transport and construction. According to international organizations, in the absence of adaptation measures, the following consequences are possible:

- reduction of economic growth to -3% by 2060 [7];
- an increase in the poverty rate by 2.7 percentage points by 2030 [7];
- a decrease in GDP to -18% by 2070 in an unfavorable scenario [9].

Of particular importance is the reduction of agricultural productivity:

- up to -37 % in rain-fed agriculture;
- up to -25 % in the irrigated sector;
- up to -20% in animal husbandry [8].

These trends have an indirect impact on the construction industry through a decrease in investment activity and demand for construction services.

Financial vulnerability is also a significant factor: about 40% of the loan portfolio of the Armenian banking system falls on climate-dependent sectors [10]. The generalized indicators are presented in table 1.

Table 1

Economic consequences of climate change in the Republic of Armenia

Indicators	Values	Source
Damage caused by climate events (25 years)	> 1.5 billion USD (\approx 0.6% of GDP/year)	[6]
Economic reduction without adaptation	up to -3% by 2060.	[7]
Rising poverty levels	+2.7 percentage points by 2030	[7]
Yield losses (rain-fed agriculture)	up to -37 % by 2050	[8]
Yield losses (irrigated agriculture)	up to -25% by 2050	[8]
Losses in animal husbandry	up to -20%	[8]
Economic losses from air pollution (related to climatic factors)	\approx 10.6 % OF GDP	[7]
Potential decline in GDP in an unfavorable scenario	up to -18 % by 2070	[9]
Vulnerability of banks' loan portfolio	\sim 40 %	[10]
Necessary investments in adaptation	\approx 8 billion USD until 2060	[7]

Analysis of the impact on the construction industry

The impact of climate change on the construction industry is systemic and manifests itself in both direct and indirect effects.

The direct impact includes:

- an increase in the cost of construction work;
- increased costs for ensuring the sustainability of facilities;
- increasing complexity of design solutions taking into account climate risks.

Indirect effects are expressed in:

- decrease in investment activity;
- increasing uncertainty of project implementation;
- changes in the structure of demand for construction services.

Additionally, the impact on the organization of construction production is increasing:

- the uncertainty of work deadlines is increasing;
- Logistics of building materials is becoming more complicated;
- The need for resource redundancy is increasing.

Thus, climate change forms a complex of interrelated risks affecting the sustainability of the construction industry.

Impact on construction production

The economic consequences of climate change have a direct and indirect impact on the construction industry of the Republic of Armenia [7,9,16].

The direct impact is manifested in:

- an increase in the cost of construction work due to the need to introduce adaptation technologies [11, 18];
- increased costs for ensuring the sustainability and safety of facilities [6,11];
- increasing complexity of design taking into account climate risks [15,17].

The indirect effect is expressed in:

- decrease in investment activity [7.16];
- instability of financial flows [9.10];
- increasing the risks of implementing construction projects [7.16];
- changes in the structure of demand for construction services [7, 16].

Additionally, climatic changes have an impact on the organization of construction production:

- the uncertainty of work completion dates is increasing [5,7];
- logistics of supplies of materials is becoming more complicated [11, 18];
- There is an increasing need to reserve resources and financial resources [10,16].

Thus, climatic changes in the Republic of Armenia form a complex of interrelated economic, social and

sectoral risks that have a significant impact on construction production [7,9,16].

In modern conditions, the construction industry should be considered not only as an object of influence of climatic factors, but also as a key tool for adapting the economy to new climatic conditions [6, 13]. This requires the integration of climate risks into the processes of strategic planning, design and construction management [15,17].

Digitalization of construction production in the context of climate change

Digitalization of construction production is one of the key areas for increasing the sustainability of the industry in the face of climate change [6,15,17]. Modern digital technologies make it possible to take into account climate risks at all stages of the life cycle of construction projects, from design to operation [15, 17].

A special role in the adaptation of construction production is played by the technology of building information modeling (BIM), which provides the possibility of integrating climatic parameters (temperature conditions, wind loads, precipitation levels) at the design stage [1,15]. This makes it possible to optimize design solutions taking into account future climatic conditions and increase the reliability of capital construction facilities [11, 18].

An additional tool for digital transformation is digital doubles of buildings and structures that provide modeling of the behavior of construction sites under extreme climatic conditions. These technologies make it possible to predict potential structural deformations, assess thermal loads, and optimize operating conditions.

The use of sensor systems and Internet of Things technologies ensures continuous monitoring of the condition of building structures, including parameters of temperature, humidity, vibrations and deformations. This allows you to quickly respond to changes in operating conditions and reduce the risks of emergencies.

Thus, digitalization of construction production is a key factor in the industry's adaptation to climate change, ensuring the transition from reactive to proactive management of construction processes.

Conclusion

The conducted research confirms that climate change has a systemic impact on the construction industry, affecting technological, organizational and economic aspects.

It has been established that changes in temperature conditions and an increase in the frequency of extreme weather events lead to changes in the properties of building materials, complication of technological processes and a decrease in the predictability of the construction cycle.

It has been revealed that in conditions of climatic instability, the role of adaptive construction management models and digital technologies, including BIM modeling and monitoring systems, is increasing.

The main directions of adaptation are:

- introduction of climate-resistant building materials;

- development of energy-efficient technologies;
- Digitalization of construction processes;
- Industrialization and modular construction;
- Implementation of climate risk management.

The results obtained confirm the need for an integrated approach to the adaptation of construction production, combining technological, organizational and economic measures.

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